

An Introduction to the GW170817 Event: Birth of Multi-Messenger Astronomy.

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Overview

The GW170817 event took place on 17th August 2017 and was the collision of 2 neutron stars, noted as one of the most intriguing events in the near history of astronomy. An event that changed the way gravitational waves were looked at, initially, gravitational waves served primarily as a confirmation of Einstein's General Relativity, and would just detect electromagnetically dark black hole mergers. Gravitational waves from the GW170817 event can now be connected to light and matter, acting as a multi-messenger tool that helps us see light from the same events and identify host galaxies.

Science behind the GW170817 event

To understand the GW170817 event, it is crucial to understand the concept of gravitational waves. These are types of waves that can be understood as ripples in spacetime and travel at the speed of light, occurring when large objects accelerate, causing distortions in spacetime that result in waves oscillating at extremely high speeds. These waves were not directly associated with electromagnetic radiation, until the GW170817 event, which led us to connect gravitational waves to light and matter, helping us to see host galaxies, and a complete picture of the universe combining gamma rays, optical rays, and gravitational waves.

Technology involved in the detection of the GW170817 event

Detecting such an event of 2 massive stars colliding requires detectors to recognize real gravitational waves. The detectors used for this event were the LIGO Hanford, LIGO Livingston, and Virgo Italy. This event took place on 17th August 2017 and was recognized as a binary neutron star merger since the chirp signal lasted around 100 seconds, longer than the black hole mergers. The reason 3 detectors were in use is that the time-delay intersection helps pinpoint the location. Furthermore, using 3 detectors, scientists assisted in triangulating the signal source using time-of-arrival differences. This improved accuracy by reducing the likelihood of false signal detections, such as those caused by local noise.

Gravitational Wave Signal: Strain – Time “Chirp Signal”

A strain-time graph represents how spacetime stretches/compresses as a gravitational wave passes by. During the GW170817 event, as gravitational waves stretched with time, signals of the wave converting into an audible signal (inside the human hearing range) produced a “chirp” sound. So, in this event, as orbital speeds increased, gravitational frequency increased, which, when converted into an audible signal, raises the pitch, sounding like a “chirp”. Allowing humans to hear spacetime oscillate.

Figure 1: High pass filtered gravitational wave strain-time signal from the GW170817 event binary neutron star merger detected by the LIGO Livingston L1 detector.

Disclaimer:

This report presents an individual analysis of GW170817 event using publicly available data online from the LIGO Open Science Center, and was conducted as an educational research project. This work has not undergone peer review.

References:

LIGO Scientific Collaboration & Virgo Collaboration (2017), GW170817: Observation of Gravitational Waves from a Binary Neutron Star Inspiral

LIGO Open Science Center, GW170817 Data Release

Data and Methods

Gravitational-wave strain data from LIGO Open Science Center

Livingston (L1) detector

Graph analyzed and plotted using Pycharm